

ADOLESCENTS AND TEACHERS CLASSROOM INTERACTIONS

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Abstract:

The task of this paper is to x-rayed adolescents and teachers classroom interactions. The researcher tried to define adolescence, adolescent, and teacher, the concept of reward and punishment as a tool to effective adolescents and teacher classroom interactions was discussed. The researcher also reviewed an article titled "Teacher-Student interactions". The key to quality classrooms, and finally, some educational implications were highlighted and conclusions were made.

Keywords: adolescents, teachers, classroom interactions

1. Introduction

Adolescence is the transitional stage of development between childhood and adulthood during which the child experiences a variety of biological changes and encounters a number of emotional issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescence covers the period of life between 10 and 20 years of age (Wikipedia (2008).

Stanley Hall denoted this period as that of "storm and stress" and according to him, conflict at this stage is normal and not unusual (Morgan, King, Weisz and Schopler, 2006). Margaret Mead, on the other hand attributed the behaviour of the adolescents to their cultures and upbringing, Chauhan (2007).

According to Anyakoha, (2015) an adolescent is the individual that is passing through the adolescence period. Adolescence period can be a turbulent as well as a dynamic period of one's life. It has been identified as a period in which young people develop abstract thinking abilities, become more aware of their sexuality, develop clear sense of identity and increase their independence from parents, Aggarwal (2007).

Mangal, (2007) stated that developmental psychologists have placed adolescence in various stages of human development. Sigmund Freud saw it as the "genital stage" of psychosexual development where the individual recaptures the sexual awareness of infancy. Jean Piaget focused on cognitive development, seeing adolescence as the "formal operative stage" where the young person develops the ability to think abstract

and draw conclusion from information available. Erick Erikson's theory of psychosocial development identified the "identity crisis" as central to the notion of adolescence. Mallum, Haggai and Ajaegbu (2004) divided adolescence period in three stages or phases. These include:

A. The prepubertal or early adolescence period

This period is characterized by changes in physical, social and psychological development. The period is also marked to growth in height and size. At this stage, girls are taller than boys.

B. The Mid-Adolescence

The adolescent at this stage is pre-occupied with considerable increase interest in sexual exploration, rebellion against constituted authorities like the parents, school and community rules and regulations. They are also involved in conformity with peer groups.

C. Late Adolescence

This stage or phase marks a turning point in the adolescents' life towards adulthood responsibilities such as career, marriage, and parenthood. This stage also marks the beginning of sense of identity. The adolescents at this stage need greater attention and assistance from both teachers and parents' in-order to achieve normal transition from childhood to adulthood. The adolescents during the adolescence period experience changes physically, mentally, socially as well as emotionally. Therefore, parents and teachers should assist the adolescents to undergo these changes with ease, Mangal, (2002). Teacher, according to National Teachers Institute (NTI) (2016) is a person who imparts knowledge or skills to other about a subject. The teacher guide learning by motivating the learners to set goals and how to attain the goals. It went on to state that teachers are the most vital factor in the implementation of educational policies and that their quality and commitment to duty determines the effectiveness of any educational system. Marzano, (2015) maintained that teachers' action in the classroom have a great impact on the students' performance. He also relates that one of the most important duty of the teacher is managing and interacting effectively with learners in the teaching/learning process. Teachers who approach classroom management and interaction as a process of maintaining effective learning environment tend to be more successful than those who place emphasis on their roles as authority figure or disciplinarians (Brophy, (2010). Research has shown that the key to successful classroom management and interaction depend on successful instruction as well as the teacher's ability to maximize the time students spend in academic activities and minimizing the time, the students spend doing nothing, because of the wise saying that an ideal mind is a devil mind, Brophy, (2010).

2. Techniques for Adolescents and Teacher Classroom Interaction

The success or failure of classroom teacher depends largely on how he/she administers the concepts of reward and punishment in his dealing with the students. Therefore, it is important for a teacher to know when and how to apply the two concepts in order to

get desired behaviour more especially in dealing with the adolescents, because what motivates children may not motivate adolescents and the punishment that may scare children may not scare adolescents. Therefore, the adolescents require special treatment from the teacher in order to have a successful interaction in the classroom; Adeyemo, (2013).

The concept of reward as it is used in schools refers to compensation offered by the school authority, teacher or any authorized person or groups of persons to a student or group of students for performance of a given tasks, good conduct or for merit. While, punishment is a social disapproval of an undesirable act resulting in personal discomfort or pain inflicted to the offender. Bello, (2014).

In normal classroom, situation teachers used reward to encourage students to work harder. Reward takes various forms and is equally used to facilitates and encourage positive response from students in the class. Reward include giving prizes to deserving students, token reinforcement, praise, award of marks, promotions, materials like cash gift, exercise books or any other gift presented to deserving students in recognition of their meritorious service or performance in their class work or in sports. Dada (1969). Reward and punishment are two forms of extrinsic motivation used in school to encourage positive behaviour and discourage negative behaviour. For, reward and punishment to be effective, the teacher need to make judicious use of both to get desired behaviour. The teacher should weigh the strength and weakness of reward and punishment to understand which is more effective in a given situation. Sogbesan, (2016)

The teacher's understanding of the concept of individual differences is very important in adolescents and teacher classroom interaction. Some noticeable differences among the adolescents of the same age group of male and female are physical, mental, emotional, temperamental as well as sex differences. Thus, the teacher bears in mind these differences before preparing for his lesson. If this is properly taken care of by the teacher, then adolescents and teacher, classroom interaction is bound to be successful. Ugwegbu, (2015).

For the teacher to interact very well with the adolescents in the classroom, he/she must understand the developmental characteristics of the adolescents. This will give him/her the upper hand in interacting with the adolescents in the classroom. Nwachuku, (2015). According to Wall, (2016) adolescents social interest, social interactions and socioeconomic condition will be of great help in organizing activities to teacher's appraisal of foster socialization. This could be done through organizing group work, quiz, debate and many group activities in the classroom. Oladele, (2016) was of the view that extra-curricula activities such as games, clubs and societies, like drama club, social club, current affairs club, press club, and field trip as well as use of resource person will go a long way in making adolescents and teacher classroom interaction more interesting.

3. Teacher-Student Interaction: The Key to Quality Classrooms

Muntner, (2008) in an article titled "Teacher-Student Interactions: The Key to Quality Classrooms" relates that every day, teachers make countless real-time decisions and facilitate dozens of interactions between themselves and their students. According to her, a programme known as "The Classroom Assessment Scoring System (CLASS)" was developed at the University of Virginia's Center for Advanced Study of Teaching and Learning. This programme (CLASS) helps educators to view classrooms through a common lens and provide support for improving the quality of teacher-student interactions and ultimately students learning.

The (CLASS) describes ten dimensions of teaching that are linked to students' achievement and social development. The ten dimensions were divided into three broad categories: emotional support, classroom organization, and instructional support. Emotional support - refers to the ways teachers help learners to develop warm, supportive relationships, experience enjoyment and excitement about learning, feel comfortable in the classroom and experience appropriate level of autonomy or independence. This includes:

- **Positive school climate** - This relates to the emotional connection that teachers have with students as well as the nature of peer interactions.
- **Negative school climate** - it is the level of expressed negativity such as anger hostility or aggression exhibited by teachers and students in the classroom.
- **Teacher sensitivity** - This refers to teachers' responsiveness to students' academic and emotional needs.
- **Regard for student perspectives** - This is the degree to which teachers' interactions with students and classroom activities place on emphasis on students interests, motivations and points of view.

3.1 Classroom organization

It refers to the ways teachers help learners to develop skills to regulate their own behaviour, get the most out of each school day and maintain interest in learning. This includes:

- **Behaviour Management** - Refers to how well teachers monitor, prevent, and redirect misbehaviour among learners.
- **Productivity** - relates to how well the classroom runs with respect to routines, how well students understand the routines, and the degree to which teachers provide activities so that maximum time can be spent in learning activities.
- **Instructional learning formats** - This refers to how teachers engage students in activities and facilitate activities so that learning opportunities are maximized.
- **Instructional support** - refers to the ways in which teachers effectively support students' cognitive development and language growth. This includes:
- **Concept development** - This refers to how teachers use instructional discussions and activities to promote students higher order thinking skills and cognition in contrast to a focus on note learning:

- **Quality of feedback** - It relates to how teachers expand participation and learning through feedback to students.
- **Language modeling** - it is the extent to which teachers stimulate, facilitate, and encourage students language use by becoming a model to the students.

Although, this study was carried out in the United States of America (U.S.A.), but if it is implemented in Nigeria will go a long way in improving teacher-student interactions more especially adolescents and teachers classroom interactions.

3.2 Educational Implications

- Teachers, as much as possible should expose adolescents to rich experiences. This will enable them to see challenging situations. For example adolescents would like to watch a court proceeding instead of a lecture on the concept of justice.
- Guided discovery methods should be used for teaching adolescents classes. The teacher could guide the adolescents' class for a project aimed at solving community based problems such as water problem, road problem, medical problem etc. Through these types of projects the adolescents thinking ability as well as social interactions can be developed.
- Teachers should help to change any negative attitudes parents have about adolescents. Also proper environment should be provided to adolescents for expression of their pent up feelings.
- Teachers should let parents know about the usefulness of using members of adolescent's peer group to build good relationships. In school, peer influence can be maintained through the creation of avenues for performing group activities such as games, club activities, excursions etc.
- The teacher has a role to play in the physical development of the adolescents. Along with parents, the teacher observes the physical progress or changes in the adolescent. He/she in turn advises parents and school authorities on the need for good health, good food and exercise that aimed at good physical fitness. Morality is an essential requirement for human coexistence, life will be meaningless and disorganized without it.
- Morality makes possible for rich and poor to live together. Therefore, the teacher should help the adolescent in achieving moral behaviour by teaching moral lessons and advising parents on moral development of their children.
- Another important role of the teacher is the emotional development of the adolescent. This achieved by encouraging positive response to both pleasant and unpleasant situations.

4. Recommendation and Conclusion

The success and failure of the teacher does not depend on his/her qualities alone but to extent largely on how he/she administers the concepts of reward and punishment (motivation) in dealing with the learners. Therefore, it is important to note that Teachers

should understand the learners characteristics, mere especially the adolescents and know when and how to use schedule of reinforcement in order to improve adolescents and teacher interaction both in the classroom and the school community in general.

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